

NORMAL SUBGROUPS AND QUOTIENT STRUCTURES OF ORTHOGONAL RHOTRIX GROUP

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Abstract

This paper studies the structure of the non-commutative orthogonal rhotrix group $OR_n(F)$ through its normal subgroups and quotient groups. The trivial subgroup and the special orthogonal rhotrix group $SOR_n(F)$, arising as the kernel of the determinant homomorphism, are shown to be normal, yielding baseline and orientation-based quotients. The centre $COR_n(F)$ is established as a normal subgroup of $OR_n(F)$, and its interaction with $SOR_n(F)$ is analyzed in the non-commutative setting. While $COR_n(F)$ need not be contained in $SOR_n(F)$, the intersection $COR_n(F) \cap SOR_n(F)$ is always normal in $SOR_n(F)$, leading to well-defined quotient that captures the intrinsic non-abelian structure of the group. Under a sufficient determinant condition on central elements, the stronger quotient $SOR_n(F)/COR_n(F)$ is obtained. These results provide a canonical quotient-based decomposition of $OR_n(F)$.

Keywords: Orthogonal rhotrix group, non-commutative groups, normal subgroups, quotient groups, determinant homomorphism, group center.

1.0 Introduction

Rhotrix theory was introduced by Ajibade [2] as a framework for the algebraic and analytical study of arrays of numbers arranged in a rhomboidal shape. The concept extends earlier ideas on matrix-tensors and matrix-noitrets studied by Atanassov and Shannon [3], while departing from classical matrix theory in both structure and operational behaviour. The initial algebraic and analytical treatment of heart-based rhotrices of order three was developed by Ajibade [2] and was subsequently generalized to higher orders by Mohammed [6], thereby establishing rhotrix theory as a viable algebraic system.

Following its introduction, rhotrix has attracted considerable interest as an underlying set for the development of various algebraic structures. In particular, several authors (Mohammed [4], [5]; Mohammed et al [7], [8]; Sani [12], [13]) have developed group-theoretic, ring-theoretic and linear-algebraic properties of rhotrices, revealing behaviours that are not always present in classical matrix settings. Of special significance is the work of Mohammed and Okon [8], who initiated a systematic study of subgroups

of non-commutative general rhotrix groups and later identified several normal subgroups and corresponding quotient groups. Their results, presented in Rhotrix Normal Subgroups and Quotient Groups, provide a foundational motivation for further investigations into quotient structures within specialized class of rhotrix groups.

Among these specialized classes is the orthogonal rhotrix group, which arises as a rhotrix analogue of the classical orthogonal matrix group. The orthogonal rhotrix group exhibits rich algebraic behaviour and, unlike its classical counterpart, may be non-commutative. Subgroups of the orthogonal rhotrix group were previously examined by Ahmed, Yisa and Ayinla [1], laying important groundwork for a deeper structural analysis. However, a comprehensive treatment of normal subgroups and quotient groups within the orthogonal rhotrix setting has remained limited.

The present work builds on these earlier contributions by undertaking a systematic study of normal subgroups and quotient groups of the non-commutative orthogonal rhotrix group. Rather than relying primarily on element-wise manipulation of rhotrix entries, this paper emphasizes structural group-theoretic methods involving homomorphism, kernels, centrality, and quotient constructions, which are particularly effective in the non-commutative setting. Nevertheless, where appropriate, concrete examples of special normal subgroups and their corresponding quotient groups are provided to illustrate the theory and reduce abstraction.

Specifically, we analyze the trivial subgroup, the kernel of the determinant homomorphism, and the center of the orthogonal rhotrix group, together with their induced quotient structures. The interaction between centrality and determinant in the non-commutative case is examined carefully, leading to sufficient conditions under which stronger quotient constructions arise. Collectively, these results yield a canonical decomposition of the orthogonal rhotrix group and contribute to the growing structural theory of rhotrix algebra.

2.0 Preliminaries

The following definitions provide the basic concepts needed for the discussion in later sections.

2.1 Rhotrices

2.1.1 Definition(Base Rhotrix)

A base rhotrix (or 3-dimensional rhotrix) is a rhomboidal arrangement of elements of a set of the form

$$R = \left\langle \begin{array}{ccc} & a & \\ b & h(R) & d \\ & e & \end{array} \right\rangle$$

where $a, b, h(R), d, e, \in \mathbb{R}$. The base rhotrix serves as the fundamental building block for constructing higher order rhotrices.

2.2 Operations on Rhotrices

2.2.1 Addition of Rhotrices

The sum of two rhotrices R and S of the same order is defined component-wise and is denoted by

$$\begin{aligned} R + S &= \left\langle \begin{array}{ccc} & a & \\ b & h(R) & d \\ & e & \end{array} \right\rangle + \left\langle \begin{array}{ccc} & f & \\ g & h(S) & j \\ & k & \end{array} \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle \begin{array}{ccc} & a + f & \\ b + g & h(R) + h(S) & d + j \\ & e + k & \end{array} \right\rangle \end{aligned}$$

It follows immediately from the definition that addition of rhotrices is commutative, that is

$$R + S = S + R$$

2.2.2 Row-column Multiplication of Rhotrices

Following Sani [13], the row-column multiplication method decomposes a rhotrix R_n into an ordered pair matrices $[a_{ij}]$ and $[b_{lk}]$, corresponding respectively to its major and minor entries. Hence, $R_n = \langle a_{ij}, c_{lk} \rangle = A_{tt}C_{(t-1)(t-1)}$

$$\begin{aligned} R_n o S_n &= \langle a_{i1j1}, c_{l1k1} \rangle o \langle b_{i2j2}, d_{l2k2} \rangle \\ &= \left\langle \sum_{i2j1}^t (a_{i1j1}, b_{i2j2}), \sum_{l2k1}^{t-1} (c_{l1k1}, d_{l2k2}) \right\rangle \end{aligned}$$

It follows from this definition that row column multiplication of rhotrices is associative but not commutative. This method of multiplication is adopted throughout this paper.

In contrast, Ajibade [2], proposed an alternative method of multiplication, known as "heart-based multiplication", which is defined in respect to the central (heart) entry of the rhotrix.

2.2.3 Identity Rhotrix

The identity rhotrix denoted as I_n with respect to row column multiplication

Let F be a field. The set of all invertible rhotrices over F consists of all rhotrices whose entries are taken from F and whose determinant are non-zero. This set is denoted by $GR_n(F)$. Thus

$$GR_n(F) = \{A_n \in R_n : \det(A_n) \neq 0\}$$

2.3.2 Set of Orthogonal Rhotrices

The set of orthogonal rhotrices, denoted by $OR_n(F)$, consists of all rhotrices over a field F for which the transpose of each rhotrix, when multiplied by the rhotrix itself, yields the identity rhotrix. Therefore, the set

$$OR_n(F) = \{A_n \in R_n(F) : A_n^T A_n = I_n\}$$

3.0 Non-commutative Orthogonal Rhotrix Group

The following result is taken from Ahmed, et al [1] and will be useful in the subsequent discussion.

Theorem 3.1 Let $OR_n(F)$ denote the set of orthogonal rhotrices and let o denote the multiplication induced by the row-column method. Then, the pair $(OR_n(F), o)$ forms a non-commutative rhotrix group of size n over F .

Proof

- Closure: Let $R_n, S_n \in OR_n(F)$. By definition of orthogonality
 $R_n^T o R_n = I_n$ and $S_n^T o S_n = I_n$

Using the properties of transpose under row-column multiplication, we have

$$(R_n o S_n)^T o (R_n o S_n) = S_n^T o R_n^T o R_n o S_n = S_n^T o I_n o S_n = S_n^T o S_n = I_n$$

Thus $OR_n(F)$ is closed under o .

- Associativity:

The row-column method of rhotrix multiplication is non-commutative but associative see Sani [13]. For all R_n, S_n , and $T_n \in OR_n(F)$.

$$(R_n o S_n) o T_n = R_n o (S_n o T_n)$$

- Identity

Let I_n denotes the identity rhotrix. Since $I_n^T = I_n$ and $I_n^T o I_n = I_n$
 It follows that $I_n \in OR_n(F)$ and I_n acts as identity element under o .

- Inverse: Let $R_n \in OR_n(F)$. Since R_n is orthogonal, we have

$$R_n^T o R_n = I_n \quad \text{and} \quad R_n o R_n^T = I_n$$

Thus, R_n^T is both a left and right inverse of R_n with respect to o . Hence every element of $OR_n(F)$ has n inverse in $OR_n(F)$.

Therefore (OR_n, o) is a group under the operation of row-column method of multiplication of rhotrices.

4.0 Normal Subgroups and Quotient Groups

4.1 Special Normal Subgroup and Quotient Group

Theorem 4.1

Let $OR_n(F)$ be the orthogonal rhotrix group and let

$$SOR_n(F) = \{A \in OR_n(F) : \det(A) = 1\}$$

Then $SOR_n(F)$ is a normal subgroup of $OR_n(F)$ and the quotient group $OR_n(F)/SOR_n(F)$ exists.

Proof

Recall that

$$OR_n(F) = \{A \in GR_n(F) : A^T A = 1\}$$

$$\beta : OR_n(F) \longrightarrow \{1, -1\} \quad \beta(A) = \det(A)$$

β is a group homomorphism

For all $A, B \in OR_n(F)$

$$\beta(AB) = \det(AB) = \det(A)\det(B) = \beta(A)\beta(B)$$

We determine the kernel β

$$\ker\beta = \{A \in OR_n(F) : \det(A) = 1\} = SOR_n(F)$$

By the first Isomorphism Theorem

$$OR_n(F)/\ker\beta \cong \text{Im}(\beta)$$

$$OR_n(F)/SOR_n \cong \mathbb{Z}_2$$

The determinant map $\beta : OR_n(F) \longrightarrow \{1, -1\}$, defined by $\beta(A) = \det(A)$, is a group homomorphism since the determinant is multiplicative. For orthogonal rhotrices, the determinant assumes only the values ± 1 . The kernel of β is the special orthogonal rhotrix group $SOR_n(F)$, which is therefore a normal subgroup of $OR_n(F)$. By the first Isomorphism Theorem, the quotient group $OR_n(F)/SOR_n$ is isomorphic to \mathbb{Z}_2 .

Corollary 4.1 (Description of the Coset of $SOR_n(F)$ in $OR_n(F)$)

Let

$$\beta : OR_n(F) \longrightarrow \{1, -1\} \quad \beta(A) = \det(A)$$

$$SOR_n(F) = \{A \in OR_n(F) : \det(A) = 1\}$$

$$A_n oSOR_n(F) = \{A \in OR_n(F) : det(A) = -1\}$$

Proof

Since β is a group homomorphism, its kernel is

$$ker\beta = \{A \in OR_n(F) : det(A) = 1\} = SOR_n(F)$$

$$OR_n(F) = \beta^{-1}(1) \cup \beta^{-1}(-1)$$

If $A_n \in OR_n(F)$ satisfies $det(A_n) = -1$, then

$$A_n oSOR_n(F) = \{A_n oS : S \in SOR_n(F)\}$$

$$det(A_n oS) = det(A_n)det(S) = -1$$

Conversely, if $A \in OR_n(F)$ with $det(A) = -1$, then

$$det(A_n^{-1}A) = det(A_n^{-1})det(A) = (-1)(-1) = 1$$

Therefore,

$$A_n oSOR_n(F) = \{A \in OR_n(F) : det(A) = -1\}$$

The quotient group $OR_n(F)/SOR_n$ is a two-element group, with identity coset $SOR_n(F)$ and non-identity coset $A_n oSOR_n(F)$ and hence

$$OR_n(F)/SOR_n \cong \mathbb{Z}_2$$

4.2 Central Normal Subgroup and quotient Group

4.2.1 Central Orthogonal Rhotrix Group

Definition 4.1

Let $(OR_n(F), o)$ be an orthogonal rhotrix group. The centre of the orthogonal rhotrix group denoted by $COR_n(F)$, is defined by

$$COR_n(F) = \{R_n \in OR_n(F) : R_n oS_n = S_n oR_n \text{ for all } S_n \in OR_n(F)\}$$

This implies that $COR_n(F)$ consists of all orthogonal rhotrices that commutes with every orthogonal rhotrix. Therefore, centre orthogonal rhotrices are rhotrices of the form $\pm I$, where I is the identity. Thus

$$COR_n(F) = \left\{ \left\langle \begin{array}{cccc} & & \pm 1 & \\ & 0 & \pm 1 & 0 \\ - & - & - & - \\ & 0 & \pm 1 & 0 \\ & & \pm 1 & \end{array} \right\rangle \right\}$$

Theorem 4.2

Let $COR_n(F)$ be the subset of $OR_n(F)$ consisting of all orthogonal rhotrices that commute with every orthogonal rhotrix and let "o" be the non-commutative method for rhotrix multiplication . Then the algebraic system $(COR_n(F), o)$ is the central orthogonal rhotrix subgroup of $(OR_n(F), o)$

Proof

We now investigate the following group axioms:

Closure:

Multiply the two possibilities

$$\begin{aligned} I_n o I_n &= I_n & I_n o -I_n &= -I_n \\ -I_n o I_n &= -I_n & -I_n o -I_n &= I_n \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the product of any two elements of $COR_n(F)$ lies in $COR_n(F)$.

Identity:

$I_n \in COR_n(F)$, so $COR_n(F)$ is non-empty and contains the identity.

Inverse:

The inverse of I_n is I_n , which is in $\pm I$ and

The inverse of $-I_n$ is $-I_n$, which is in $\pm I$

Thus the elements of $COR_n(F)$ are their own inverse.

Therefore, the central orthogonal rhotrix group is a subgroup of the orthogonal rhotrix group.

$$(COR_n(F), o) \leq (OR_n(F), o)$$

Theorem 4.3

Let $OR_n(F)$ be an orthogonal rhotrix group and let

$$COR_n(F) = \{R_n \in OR_n(F) : R_n o S_n = S_n o R_n \text{ for all } S_n \in OR_n(F)\}$$

Then the pair $(COR_n(F), o)$ is a normal subgroup of $(OR_n(F), o)$.

Proof

We have established that $(COR_n(F), o) \leq (OR_n(F), o)$. Now, to prove normality, let $S_n \in OR_n(F)$ and let $R_n \in COR_n(F)$. Since R_n commutes with every element of $OR_n(F)$, in particular with S_n , we have

$$\begin{aligned} S_n o R_n &= R_n o S_n \\ S_n o R_n o S_n^{-1} &= R_n o S_n o S_n^{-1} = R_n \end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$S_n o R_n o S_n^{-1} \in COR_n(F)$$

Since this holds for all $S_n \in OR_n(F)$ and all $R_n \in COR_n(F)$, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} S_n COR_n(F) S_n^{-1} &\subseteq COR_n(F) \\ COR_n(F) &\trianglelefteq OR_n(F) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the centre of the orthogonal rhotrix group is a normal subgroup. This result shows that normality of the centre is intrinsic and does not depend on determinants, orthogonality conditions, or commutativity of the group operation. In particular, for non-commutative orthogonal rhotrix groups, the centre always forms a normal subgroup.

Theorem 4.4 Quotient by the Centre of an Orthogonal Rhotrix Group

Let $OR_n(F)$ be an orthogonal rhotrix group and let

$$\begin{aligned} COR_n(F) &= \{R_n \in OR_n(F) : R_n o S_n = S_n o R_n \text{ for all } S_n \in OR_n(F)\} \\ OR_n(F)/COR_n(F) &= \{R_n o COR_n(F) : R_n \in OR_n(F)\} \\ (R_n o COR_n(F)) o (T_n o COR_n(F)) &= (R_n o T_n) o COR_n(F) \end{aligned}$$

Proof

The proof is established through quotient group via normal subgroup theorem.

From previous result, $COR_n(F) \trianglelefteq OR_n(F)$. By Normal Subgroup Theorem, whenever

$$H \trianglelefteq G,$$

the set of left cosets

$$\begin{aligned} G/H &= \{mH : m \in G\} \\ (mH)(nH) &= (mn)H \end{aligned}$$

Applying the result with $G = OR_n(F)$ and $H = COR_n(F)$, it follows that the set

$$\begin{aligned} OR_n(F)/COR_n(F) &= \{R_n o COR_n(F) : R_n \in OR_n(F)\} \\ (R_n o COR_n(F)) o (T_n o COR_n(F)) &= (R_n o T_n) o COR_n(F) \end{aligned}$$

Hence the quotient group $OR_n(F)/COR_n(F)$ exists.

4.2.2 The Centre of the Orthogonal Rhotrix Group and its Relation to the Special Orthogonal Rhotrix Group

Let $OR_n(F)$ denote the orthogonal rhotrix group and let

$$COR_n(F) = \{R_n \in OR_n(F) : R_n o S_n = S_n o R_n \text{ for all } S_n \in OR_n(F)\}$$

$$SOR_n(F) = \{A \in OR_n(F) : \det(A) = 1\}$$

Centrality Versus Determinant

Centrality and determinant are, in general, independent properties.

An element of $OR_n(F)$ may commute with all other elements while having determinant $+1$ or -1 . Consequently, there is no a priori reason for the centre $COR_n(F)$ to be contained in $SOR_n(F)$.

In particular, if there exists a central orthogonal rhotrix A such that $\det(A) = -1$, then

$$A \in COR_n(F) \setminus SOR_n(F), \quad COR_n(F) \not\subseteq SOR_n(F)$$

Guaranteed Inclusion

Regardless of the determinant behaviour of central elements, the intersection

$$COR_n(F) \cap SOR_n(F)$$

$$COR_n(F) \cap SOR_n(F) \subseteq SOR_n(F)$$

Thus, the quotient group

$$SOR_n(F) / (COR_n(F) \cap SOR_n(F))$$

. Conditional Inclusion

The inclusion

$$COR_n(F) \subseteq SOR_n(F)$$

$$COR_n(F) = COR_n(F) \cap SOR_n(F)$$

Thus, the quotient group

$$SOR_n(F) / COR_n(F)$$

This situation mirrors the classical orthogonal group $O(n)$, where the centre is $\pm I$ and the inclusion $C(O(n)) \subseteq SO(n)$ depends on the parity of n . Similarly, in the orthogonal rhotrix setting, the determinant of central elements must be analyzed explicitly and can not be inferred from centrality alone.

Theorem 4.5 Sufficient Condition

Suppose that the centre $COR_n(F)$ of n orthogonal rhotrix group satisfies $\det(R_n) = 1$ for all $R_n \in COR_n(F)$.

$$COR_n(F) \subseteq SOR_n$$

. Proof

By definition

$$SOR_n(F) = \{A \in OR_n(F) : \det(A) = 1\}$$

$$R_n \in SOR_n(F) \quad \text{for all } R_n \in COR_n(F)$$

$$COR_n(F) \subseteq SOR_n(F)$$

The inclusion $COR_n(F) \subseteq SOR_n(F)$ is not automatic but holds under the explicit and variable condition that all central orthogonal rhotrices have determinant one.

In general, the quotient $SOR_n(F)/COR_n(F) \cap SOR_n(F)$ is always well defined. However, in this work we adopt the stronger quotient $SOR_n(F)/COR_n(F)$ under the sufficient condition that every central orthogonal rhotrix has determinant one, so that $COR_n(F) \subseteq SOR_n(F)$.

Theorem 4.6

Let OR_n be an orthogonal rhotrix group, let $SOR_n(F)$ be the special orthogonal rhotrix group and let $COR_n(F)$ denote the centre of $OR_n(F)$. If $COR_n(F) \subseteq SOR_n(F)$, then the quotient group $SOR_n(F)/COR_n(F)$.

$$(A_n o COR_n(F)) o (B_n o COR_n(F)) = (A_n o B_n) o COR_n(F)$$

Proof

From previous results, $COR_n(F) \trianglelefteq OR_n(F)$. Since $COR_n(F) \subseteq SOR_n(F) \leq OR_n(F)$, it follows that

$$COR_n(F) \trianglelefteq SOR_n(F)$$

Hence, by Normal Subgroup Theorem, the set of cosets

$$SOR_n(F)/COR_n(F) = \{A_n o COR_n : A \in SOR_n(F)\}$$

$$(A_n o COR_n(F)) o (B_n o COR_n(F)) = (A_n o B_n) o COR_n(F)$$

4.3 Trivial Normal Subgroup and Quotient Group**Definition 4.2**

The trivial subgroup of $OR_n(F)$ is $\{I_n\} = \{I_n\}$.

Proposition 4.1 (Normality of the Trivial Subgroup)

The trivial subgroup I_n is a normal subgroup of $OR_n(F)$.

Proof

For any $R_n \in OR_n(F)$

$$R_n o \{I_n\} o R_n^{-1} = \{I_n\}$$

Proposition 4.2(Quotient by the Trivial Subgroup)

The quotient group $OR_n(F)/I_n$ exists and is isomorphic to $OR_n(F)$.

Proof

Since I_n is normal, the quotient $OR_n(F)/I_n$ is well defined.

Each coset has the form

$$Ao\{I\} = \{A\}, \quad A \in OR_n(F)$$

$$\beta : OR_n(F) \longrightarrow OR_n(F)/I_n \quad \beta(A) = A\{I\}$$

We verify

Homomorphism:

$$\beta(AB) = (AB)I = (A\{I\})(B\{I\}) = \beta(A)\beta(B)$$

Injective:

If $\beta(A) = \beta(B)$, then $AI = BI$, so $A = B$

Surjective

Every coset is of the form AI , so β is onto. Thus , β is bijective homomorphism, and therefore

$$OR_n(F)/I_n \cong OR_n(F).$$

Since the trivial subgroup I contains only the identity rhotrix, each coset AI consists of a single element. Consequently, the quotient group $OR_n(F)/I_n$ is in bijective correspondence with $OR_n(F)$, and the induced operation coincides with the original multiplication in $OR_n(F)$. Hence, $OR_n(F)/I_n$ is canonically isomorphic to $OR_n(F)$.

Corollry 4.1

The trivial subgroup I_n is also a normal subgroup of $SOR_n(F)$, and

$$SOR_n(F)/I_n \cong SOR_n(F).$$

5.0 Subgroup Lattice of the Orthogonal Rhotrix Group

Below is the subgroup lattice diagram involving $COR_n(F)$, $SOR_n(F)$ and $OR_n(F)$.

are listed therein, forms a special normal subgroup of $(FOR_5(F), o)$ under the same binary operation as that defined on $(FOR_5(F), o)$.

$$NOR_5(F) = \left\langle \begin{matrix} 1 & & & & \\ & 0 & 1 & 0 & \\ & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ & & 0 & 1 & 0 & \\ & & & & 1 & \end{matrix} \right\rangle, D = \left\langle \begin{matrix} & & & 0 & & \\ & 0 & 1 & 1 & & \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \\ & & 0 & 1 & 1 & \end{matrix} \right\rangle, E = \left\langle \begin{matrix} & & & & & 0 \\ & 1 & 1 & 0 & & \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & \\ & & 1 & 1 & 0 & \\ & & & & & 0 \end{matrix} \right\rangle$$

Table 5.1 Multiplication table for $(NOR_5(F), o)$.

\circ	A	D	E
A	A	D	E
B	B	C	F
C	C	F	B
D	D	E	A
E	E	A	D

The left cosets of $NOR_5(F)$ in $FOR_5(F)$ are $\{A, D, E\}$ and $\{B, C, F\}$. Consequently, these cosets form the elements of the quotient group $FOR_5(F)/NOR_5(F)$, with the corresponding Cayley table given below.

Table 5.2 Multiplication table for $(FOR_5(F)/NOR_5(F), o)$

\circ	$\{A, D, E\}$	$\{B, C, F\}$
$\{A, D, E\}$	$\{A, D, E\}$	$\{B, C, F\}$
$\{B, C, F\}$	$\{B, C, F\}$	$\{A, D, E\}$

6.0 Conclusion

In this paper, we have presented a systematic study of the normal subgroups and quotient groups of the non-commutative orthogonal rhotrix group. By focusing on canonical constructions arising from identity, determinant, and centrality considerations, we identified all structurally induced normal subgroups and examined their associated quotient groups. The trivial subgroup was shown to yield a baseline quotient isomorphic to the original group, while the determinant homomorphism produced the special orthogonal rhotrix group as a normal subgroup and led to a two-coset decomposition distinguishing orientation-preserving and orientation-reversing rhotrices.

We further established that the centre of the orthogonal rhotrix group is always normal, but its inclusion in the special orthogonal rhotrix group is not automatic in the non-commutative setting. This observation motivated the analysis of the intersection of the centre with the special orthogonal rhotrix group and the formulation of a sufficient determinant condition under which

stronger quotient structures arise. The resulting quotients capture the intrinsic non-abelian behavior of the orthogonal rhotrix group and provide a refined understanding of its internal symmetry structure.

The results obtained offer canonical quotient based decomposition of the orthogonal rhotrix group and extend existing work on rhotrix algebra by clarifying the roles of orientation, commutativity, and central symmetry. These findings provide a foundation for further research on representations, automorphism groups, and applications of orthogonal rhotrices in algebra and related areas.

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